

Comparative Relationship between ... (Aybenagha & Nduka, 2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15044767>

Comparative Relationship between Cyber security Measures and Protection of Intellectual Property among University Staff in Rivers State, Nigeria

Avbenagha Eseoghene Andrew¹
eseoghene.avbenagha@descoem.edung
+2348035407337

Nduka Nkechi Ntaka-Joshua²
nduka.joshua2018@yahoo.com
+2349058886684

¹Department of Integrated Science, Delta State College of Education Mosogar.

²Department of Curriculum studies and Instructional Technology, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Port Harcourt

Abstract

Universities in Rivers State, Nigeria, have experienced cybercrime, thereby creating significant security threats to the university system. The researchers sought a comparative relationship between cybersecurity measures and protection of intellectual property among universities staff in Rivers- State using: firewall hardware, antivirus software, and physical security measures to protect intellectual properties. The correlation research design was used for this study, while the population consisted of one thousand hundred (1500) respondents comprising of industrial training (IT) staff, academic staff, and students, all in Rivers- State universities. The sample size was 100, using the stratified random sampling technique, employed to ensure a concise representation from the sub-groups. Research questions were analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) method for both the research questions and hypotheses used in the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS). The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled, 'Cybersecurity Measures and Protection of Intellectual Property' (CMPIQ) while questionnaires were distributed through online platforms in Google Forms or Survey Monkey and physical forms, while the Cronbach alpha was used to determine the instrument's reliability index, which yielded 0.87. Findings of the study showed that firewall hardware, antivirus software, and physical security significantly had an effect on protecting intellectual properties. It was recommended, among others, that the government and the university system should deepen campaigns on cybercrime awareness and punish offenders under the criminal act and conviction to ensure that academic excellence is upheld.

Keywords: Cybersecurity, Protection, Intellectual Property & University

Introduction

Intellectual property in tertiary institutions has persistently witnessed a global explosion in counterfeiting, plagiarism, and piracy, creating an atmosphere of significant threats to the university system. (Evelyn, 2014). Statistics show that Nigeria loses about N127 billion annually to cybercrime, while Abayo *et al* (2021) mentioned that cybercrimes in this region are flourishing expansively in Nigeria, undetected while the university system is no exception since cybersecurity might be a possible medium to protect intellectual properties due to cyber frauds that has infiltrated into the academic system. Conspicuously, leading universities in Nigeria and Morocco have also suffered major breaches, illustrating the widespread nature of the issue across (Bukhari & Samuel, 2021). Cybersecurity, the protection of computer systems and networks from cyberattacks, serves as a central defensive system among intellectual property assets in all institutions (Vaza *et al.*, 2024). Cybercrime hits all sectors, but the worst hit is the educational system, where potentials are robbed of their academic virtues; cybersecurity could set the pace by standing out as a defensive mechanism against intellectual properties. Cybersecurity are sets of rules and technological measures used in protecting the internet, a practice that shields computers, servers, mobile devices, electronic systems, networks, and data from malicious attacks through information technology security or electronic information security. It promotes adequate mechanisms that protect university intellectual property. (Premkumar, Yemi, & Anil, 2024). The essence is to combat threats in the universities through strict and adopted cybersecurity protocols by creating more awareness among students, staff, and faculty on security risks; consolidating technological infrastructure towards better openness in monitoring; and deploying security tools by protecting the domain name services that will in turn block access to malicious websites.

Comparative Relationship between ... (Aybenagha & Nduka, 2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15044767>

Chinyere (2018) mentioned that universities in Rivers State have also experienced massive cybercrimes. While Akpan (2016) reported that cybercrime has put Nigerian students in a serious quest for money other than the quest to study. Meaning that everyone is a threat to the real pact of cyber security in the Nigerian university since they have a part to play and expose the hackers themselves. These lapses have created room for patentability because of the urge to get quick money other than preserving the integrity of the universities in the nation. Intellectual properties in this region could be preserved by using firewall hardware, antivirus software, and physical security measures. Firewall hardware is an appliance that comes between the uplink and the client system that filters traffic that gets through pre-configured security policies and user profiles to protect university rules through the use of strong passwords that should not be compromised. Felicia, et al (2022). This uplink serves to allow incoming traffic from public or private networks without piracy, while the client system, a server, an employee desktop, a WFH system, and an IoT node. (Chiradeep, 2022) that protects the system. Antivirus displays devices against known threats and eliminates them from infecting one's devices instantly using reliable security software like Norton Plus or Kaspersky to shield one's personal data and protect the intellectual properties of students and staff from hackers, malware, viruses, and online threats, ensuring that adequate physical security measures are taken to destabilize cybercrimes in Rivers- State universities. (Lois, 2022).

Intellectual properties are rated as the, ' crown jewel 'for the university because they provide vehicles for the universities to project their unique norms and objectives into the international marketplace, at the same time, reap a financial benefit in which Nigeria university must uphold in preserving their intellectual property since it tends to rob academic intellectuals of their long aged suffering in the academic system, through research and development (R&D) activities that produces undiluted result among dedicated students and staff through inventions while intellectual properties such as: trademarks, journals/textbooks, projects are critically considered in industrial designs- logos, music, books, curriculum, journals, scientific drawings . These properties should not be taken for granted; rather, adequate cyber security should be mapped out to ensure that professional measures are granted to avert compromise in the university system. Felicia *et al* (2022). Rivers-state universities must adhere to adequate measures towards encryption on their system with authenticated passwords to ensure that authors and editors of books and journals in scholarly articles are preserved. In addition, students, lecturers, and library staff must be sensitized on the pact of this chronicle expedition by ensuring that they avert book piracy (consciously or unconsciously) through photocopying, scanning, and printing of copyright material, while the law must take its course in line with Section 38(3) of the Copyright Act with strict provisions that empower the copyright inspector to prosecute, conduct, or defend before court any charge, information, complaint, or order proceedings arising under the Act, while stiffer measures should be promulgated to discourage intending cybercrime activities. Signals reports growing and more sophisticated cases of cybercrimes that leverage technology experts, especially in the university system where academics is a top priority (Chiradeep, 2022).

Record of Cybercrimes in Nigerian Universities

1. The prevalence of Denial of Service (DoS) attack in which an unknown person tampered with the Network Time Protocol (NTP) server in the Federal University of Technology Akure (Mojeed, 2020).
2. Madonna University in Eastern Nigeria also reported that hackers accessed and tempered with over 25,000 data points in their database (Egbunike, 2019).
3. In 2016, 2017, and 2018, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria, disclosed incidents that potentially exposed a serious breach in the university website that resulted in a compromise of students and staff data (Bukhari, 2018).
4. In another incident, a university staffer was found compromising the admission records and printing fake admission letters for some applicants (Bukhari, 2018), were staff members of the Management Information System (MIS) Unit was apprehended for breaching the security protocols and conniving with some students of the university to illegally allocate rooms and print admission letters.

Statement of the Problem

Intellectual property in the universities have witnessed massive global manipulations in counterfeiting, plagiarism, and piracy, especially at Rivers State University. Felicia et al. (2022) espoused on the relationship between cybercrime and good governance in tertiary institutions in Rivers State, while Bukhari and Samuel (2021) tested gunned on the framework in managing cybercrime risks in Nigeria. These studies have created awareness of significant threats to the university system on inadequacies in data security framework, data loss management, and physical implementation but have not addressed the gap on cybercrimes being successful at encroaching and manipulating vital documents, in spite of a large chunk of money invested

Comparative Relationship between ...(Aybenagha & Nduka, 2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15044767>

in the fight at national levels, even across borders. The quest on protecting Rivers State University intellectual properties has necessitated this research to strengthen the field of cybersecurity through data management and encourage the growth of institutional repositories in order to address lapses in intellectual properties. Therefore, the study explores the comparative relationship between cybersecurity measures and the protection of intellectual property among university staff in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

Specifically, the purpose of this study was to:

1. Determine the relationship between firewall and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University?
2. Determine the extent of the relationship between antivirus software and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University?
3. Determine the extent of the relationship between physical security measures and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University?

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the extent of relationship between firewall and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University?
2. What is the extent of the relationship between antivirus software and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University?
3. What is the extent of the relationship between physical security measures and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between firewall and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University

H₀₂: There is no relationship between among between antivirus software and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University

H₀₃: There is no significant the relationship physical security measures and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University

Methodology

The correlation research design was used for this study and the population consists of 1500 one thousand hundred respondents (IT staff, Academic staff and students) who were gotten from Rivers State University. The sample size was 100, while the stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure representation from sub-groups. The instrument used for data collection was a thirty-item structured questionnaire on a 4-point Likert type developed and validated by experts in measurement and evaluation. These research questions were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) method for both the research questions and hypotheses with the use of the statistical packaged for social sciences (SPSS). The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled cyber security measures and protection of intellectual property Questionnaire CMPIPQ). The questionnaires were distributed through online platforms such as Google forms or survey monkey and physical form while the Cronbach alpha was used to determine the instrument’s reliability index, which yielded 0.87.

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between firewall and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State Universities.

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient Analysis of firewall and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University. Correlations

Correlation	Fire wall	Protection of intellectual property
-------------	-----------	-------------------------------------

Comparative Relationship between ...(Aybenagha & Nduka, 2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15044767>

Firewall	Pearson Correlation	1	.845**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Protection of intellectual property	Pearson Correlation	.845**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The result shows there is a high positive correlation between firewall and protection of intellectual property ($r=-0.85$) and the relationship is significant ($p=0.00$). The result means that as scores on firewall increase, there is a corresponding increase in protection of intellectual property. Since the associated p-value was lesser than 0.05, it therefore suggests that there is a significant relationship between firewall and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Hypothesis Two: There is no relationship between antivirus software and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University. The following table answered research question 2 and analyses hypothesis 2

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient Analysis of antivirus software and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University

Correlation	Antivirus software	Protection of intellectual property
Antivirus software	Pearson Correlation	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.691**
	N	100
Protection of Intel lecture property	Pearson Correlation	.691**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The result shows that there is a high positive correlation between Antivirus software and protection of intellectual property ($r=0.69$) and the relationship is significant ($p=0.00$). The result means that as scores on antivirus software increase, there is a corresponding increase in protection of intellectual property. Since the associated p-value was lesser than 0.05, it, therefore, suggests that there is a significant relationship between antivirus software and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between physical security measures and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State

Correlation	Physical security measure	Protection of intellectual property
Physical security measure	Pearson Correlation	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.603**
	N	100
Protection of Intellectual property	Pearson Correlation	.603**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The result shows there is a high positive correlation between physical security measures and protection of intellectual property in tertiary institutions ($r=0.60$) and the relationship is significant ($p=0.00$). The result means that as scores on physical security increase, there is a corresponding increase protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State. Since the associated

Comparative Relationship between ...(Aybenagha & Nduka, 2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15044767>

p-value was higher than 0.05, it, therefore, suggests that there is a significant relationship between physical security measures and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Relationship between firewall and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University

Findings of the study revealed that staff in Rivers State University recognized firewalls as a primary defense mechanism for preventing unauthorized access to sensitive data. Firewalls serve as a critical component of cyber security infrastructure, offering protection against unauthorized access, data breaches, and other cyber threats that could compromise intellectual property (IP). This finding aligns with the work of Singh and Kaur (2023), who noted that firewalls create a virtual barrier that monitors and controls incoming and outgoing network traffic based on predetermined security rules.

Relationship between antivirus software and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State University

The findings of the study revealed significant insights into how antivirus programs contribute to safeguarding intellectual assets. The study found that most staff members at Rivers State University rely on antivirus software as a primary tool for protecting intellectual property. This finding is supported by Olayemi and Adebayo (2021) who noted that antivirus software detects and neutralizes malware that could lead to data breaches and the loss of proprietary information.

Relationship between physical security measures and protection of intellectual property among staff in Rivers State

The findings of the study revealed the importance of tangible security practices in safeguarding intellectual assets. Physical security measures such as controlled access to facilities and surveillance systems, play a complementary role in protecting IP from theft, loss, or unauthorized access. Statistical analysis revealed a positive correlation between robust physical security measures and the protection of intellectual property. This corresponds with the study by Adeyemi and Chukwu (2019) which established that physical security is foundational in preventing IP theft, particularly in academic environments.

Conclusion

Rivers-State universities have consistently addressed unauthorized access to intellectual properties, but more has to be done to avert hackers from gaining access to the university system by ensuring that adequacies are employed to serve as a defensive tool in the intellectual property of the university system, especially in the use of antivirus, firewalls, and physical security. Notwithstanding, the embracement of these security measures must be harnessed to salvage consistent fraud and irregularities if adequate propensity is attached to the security of universities intellectual properties to widen productivity and secure the university system.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made, to serve as cyber security measures and protection of intellectual property among staff of Rivers State University

1. Government and the university system should deepen campaigns on cybercrime awareness on intellectual properties in order to make them understand that cyber security is the only way out where offenders are punishable under the criminal act and conviction.
2. Schools should set up a training program that can be conducted to improve staff understanding of firewalls and their role in IP protection
3. Undergraduates could be caught young through sensitization programs and afterwards given functional education that should be in line with vocational skills.
4. Implementation is key to national productivity, as such, government should deploy measures to ensure that intellectual properties are given ultimate concern, while sensitive information should be kept secret and always updated from the university website.

References

Abayo, S, Usman, S, Mohammed, K. T, Muhammad, A (2021). Cyber security and Cybercrime in Nigeria: The Implication on National Security and Digital. Economy. *Journal of Intelligence and Cyber security book of Sociology*, 2(2), 181-186.

Comparative Relationship between ... (Aybenagha & Nduka, 2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15044767>

- Adeyemi., & and Chukwu, P. (2019) The role of physical security in intellectual property management in Nigerian universities. *African Journal of Security Studies*,8(4).145-161.
- Akpan, E.E (2016) Cyber security and Resilience in Nigeria and Reduction of Cyber Risks. International King-Uk. *International Journal of Academic Anthology*
- Bukhari, B. (2018). Effects of Security Protocols on Cybercrime in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria [Academic Masters, *University of KwaZulu Natal, South Africa.*
- Bukhari, B & Samuel, C (2021). Framework for Managing Cybercrime Risks in Nigerian *Universities Proceedings of the 1st Virtual Conference on Implications of Information and Digital Technologies for Development.*
- Chinyere. Amini-Philips "Awareness and Involvement in Cybercrime among Undergraduate Students in Universities in Rivers State, Nigeria". *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention (IJHSSI)*
- Chiradeep, B. (2022) Top 10 Firewall Hardware Devices in 2022. <https://www.spiceworks.com/itsecurity/networksecurity/articles/top10firewallhardwaredevices/#~:text=Firewall%20software%20is%20usually%20copyright> Act Cap C28. Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004
- Egbunike, N. (2019). Nigerian students face cybercrime charges for criticizing their university online. <https://globalvoices.org/2019/07/11/nigerian-students-face-cybercrime-charges-for-criticizing-their-university-online>
- Ekpoh, U. I., Edet, A. O., & Ukpog, N. N. (2020). Security Challenges in Universities: Implications for Safe School Environment. *Journal of Educational and Social Research.*
- Evelyn, C. G. (2014). (Reducing Book Piracy: The Role of the Higher Education Sector *International Research in Education ISSN 2327-5499*
- Felicia, King-Agbot, Daniel, O, Chizoma, C. O (2022). Relationship between Cybercrime and Good Governance in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State *Approaches in International Journal of Research Development: ISSN 2141-1409*
- Kaspersky, A. O (2021). Tips on how to protect yourself against cybercrime www.kaspersky.com/resource
- Kunle. A 'Global Software Piracy' Business Alliance Software Magazine, May 11, 2012, P.
- Lois, C. (2022) what is antivirus? Definition, types and Benefits <https://us.norton.com/blog/malware/what-is-antivirus>
- Marcus, O.B. (2021). What are the types of cyber-attacks that could impact my school? www.9ine.com/news blog?
- Mojeed, M. (2020). How Nigerian University Launched Massive Cyber-attacks Against Premium Times. <https://allafrica.com/stories/202007280025.html>
- Nwibani, Q. L. (2021). Intellectual Property, SMEs, and Economic Recovery in Nigeria
- Ola, W (2024). How African universities can protect data from cyber attacks. <https://punchng.com/how-african-universities-can-protect-data-from-cyber-attacks/> Retrieved 22/10/2024
- Olayemi, T., & Adebayo, M. (2021). The role of antivirus software in protecting intellectual property. *Journal of Digital Security.*
- Premkumar, R, Yemi, A & Anil, K. J. (2024). Implementation of Machine Learning Techniques for Cloud Security in Detection of DDOS Attacks. *International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology (IJCET)*
- Singh, R., & Kaur, S. (2023) Comprehensive firewall solutions: Protecting intellectual property in the digital age. *Cyber Tech Review*
- Solomon, V.A (2023) Cybersecurity in Nigeria: Evaluating of Existing Framework for the Prohibition of Cybercrimes, The challenges and Recommendation for Improvement
- Vaza, Rahul, N. et al. (2024). Security and Privacy Concerns in AI-Enabled Educational Frameworks: *An in Depth Analysis "Educational Administration: Theory and Practice 30.4(2024) 8436-8445*
- Virgil. V. D. R Intellectual Property and Higher Education: 'DOI: 10.5929/20